

CALPHAD thermodynamics for OPC clinker mineralogy prediction

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Abstract

Cement producers are increasingly adopting alternative fuels (AFs), e.g., plastic waste, used tires, biomass, and sewage sludge, to reduce the environmental footprint. These introduce additional components into the kiln, impacting the mineralogy and performance of Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC) clinker by the formation of specific polymorphs or new compounds in the product. Leveraging the Calculation of Phase Diagrams (CALPHAD) method, this study evaluates existing commercial thermodynamic databases, including FactSage's FTOxid and GTOX. Additionally, it assesses their applicability to OPC clinker mineralogy predictions by a two-step model based on raw materials chemical composition and considering minor element insertion (MgO, Na₂O, K₂O, SO₃, MnO₂, P₂O₅, TiO₂, SiO₂, Al₂O₃, and Fe₂O₃). The output of the model, as main mineralogical phases (C₃S, C₂S, C₃A and C₄AF), is benchmarked with experimental mineralogical compositions from literature that used Laboratory XRD and Synchrotron XRD Rietveld analysis. Results show that FactSage's FTOxid database performs poorly, showing no Alite (C₃S) for all simulated cases; whereas GTOX database yields a better outcome, achieving a similar overall performance with Bogue's equations in clinker mineralogical prediction leaving significant room for refinement to improve accuracy and applicability. This study demonstrates that an optimization of clinker composition and process control is feasible via CALPHAD-based models with their improved Gibbs energy datasets. This supports the cement industry efforts to reduce AF-induced variability directly lowering CO₂ emissions and energy consumption in clinker production.

Keywords: CALPHAD method; Clinker; Portland cement; Thermodynamic calculations.

1 Introduction

The production of Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC) clinker remains a cornerstone of modern construction, yet its high-energy demand and environmental footprint necessitate rigorous optimization. As cement industries increasingly adopt alternative fuels (AFs)—such as plastic waste, biomass, or sewage sludge—to reduce reliance on fossil resources, the introduction of trace elements like MgO, Na₂O, K₂O,

SO_3 , MnO_2 , P_2O_5 , and TiO_2 into clinker systems poses new challenges to traditional mineralogical prediction. These minor components can modify, stabilize and destabilize phase equilibria critical for forming major clinker mineral phases (C_3S , C_2S , C_3A , C_4AF), potentially compromising clinker reactivity and energy efficiency.

As all chemical reactions are governed by the fundamental law of thermodynamics, a sensible approach is to model the clinker formation reaction via the CALPHAD methodology. Which is appealing as it allows to calculate stable and metastable multicomponent thermodynamic equilibria with a large number of elements, if the relevant Gibbs energy databases are available.

The first series of simulations using the CALPHAD approach for cement clinker formation were published in [1] in the year 2000. More recent work was presented in [2, 3]; however, in all cases, only general thermodynamic databases were applied, as provided by software suppliers and the validity and the limitations of the simulation results were not discussed thoroughly.

The most complete Gibbs energy databases for oxides and salts are provided within the FactSage Gibbs energy minimizer software package [4]. Two datasets are available: FTOxid (v.8.3, by ThermFact) and GTOX (by GTT-Technologies). The main difference between these is the thermodynamic modeling of the liquid phase. In the former, the modified quasi-chemical model is used [5], whereas the latter uses an associate model [6] to model short range interaction. The approaches are equivalent, but it is generally admitted that the quasi-chemical model leads to better extrapolation results in higher order systems [5] and presents a lower number of adjustable model interaction parameters that are fitted to reproduce the experimental information.

The purpose of this work is to discuss the contents of the Gibbs energy databases in FTOxid and GTOX and their pertinence in the modeling of the clinker formation process when accounting for minor element insertion present in AFs. The thermodynamic models for all major and minor clinker phases are compared, and benchmark calculations are carried out to check the validity of the proposed approach.

2 Gibbs energy database

The available Gibbs energy models for the mineralogical phases of a clinker are summed up in Table 1 – in which the underrepresentation of the phases' minor element insertion is critical for Alite (C_3S), accounting only for Sr into the crystal lattice of the phase in FTOxid database and no minor element insertion on GTOX. Regarding the phases present, only one polymorph in both commercial databases is characterized. Its Gibbs energy corresponds to the rhombohedral high temperature modification of C_3S . A more complete thermodynamic description of Belite (C_2S) and its various modifications are available in GTOX with three of its major mineralogical phases and Fe, Mg and P in solid solution are modelled.

For FTOxid, the prior polymorphs and element insertions plus Sr are represented. The separation in FTOxid of the full solid solution of $\alpha\text{-C}_2\text{S}$ and C_3P can create the illusion that phosphorous insertion is considered, but interactions and solid

solubility with the other elements are not characterized. The description of two different datasets is artificial and may lead to calculation errors when considerable amounts of P are present. Note that alkali insertion and industrially observed β -C₂S modification – essential in polymorph stabilization and cement production – are missing in both databases.

Table 1. Overview of the models used for the main clinker phases in FTOxid and GTX (FactSage v. 8.3) as compared to literature data.

Phase	FTOxid	GTOX	Literature
Alite (C₃S)	C ₃ S – (Ca,Sr) ₃ SiO ₅	C ₃ S – Ca ₃ SiO ₅	Triclinic: T1, T2, T3 Monoclinic: M1, M2, M3 Rhombohedral: R [8] Replacement of Ca ²⁺ by Mg ²⁺ [9], Na ⁺ [10], K ⁺ [10], Fe ²⁺ [9] Replacement of Si ⁴⁺ by Al ³⁺ [9], Fe ³⁺ [9], Mn ³⁺ [11], Ti ⁴⁺ [11], P ⁵⁺ [12] Interstitial insertion: Al ³⁺ [13], Na ⁺ [10]
Belite (C₂S)	Olivine (Ca,Fe,Mg)[Ca,Fe,Mg]SiO ₄ Alpha-prime (Ca,Sr) ₂ SiO ₄ dilute Mg, Fe Alpha (Ca,Sr) ₂ SiO ₄ dilute Fe, Mg α -C ₂ S-C ₃ P (Ca ₂ SiO ₄ , Ca ₃ P ₂ O ₈) solution not compatible with solutions above	Olivine (Ca,Fe,Mg)[Ca,Fe,Mg]SiO ₄ Alpha-prime (Ca,Fe,Mg, \square) ₂ (Si,P)O ₄ Alpha (Ca,Fe,Mg, \square) ₂ (Si,P)O ₄	γ phase α' _L phase α' _H phase α phase β phase [14] Replacement of Ca ²⁺ by Mg ²⁺ [15], Na ⁺ [16], K ⁺ [17], Sr ²⁺ [16], Fe ²⁺ [18] Replacement of Si ⁴⁺ by Al ³⁺ [17], Fe ³⁺ [18], Ti ⁴⁺ [18], P ⁵⁺ [14], S ⁶⁺ [14]

Table 1. Overview of the models used for the main clinker phases in FTOxid and GTOX (FactSage v. 8.3) as compared to literature data. (Continued)

Phase	FTOXid	GTOX	Literature
Aluminate (C₃A)	Cubic Ca ₃ (Al,Fe) ₂ O ₆ (Ca,Sr) ₃ Al ₂ O ₆	C ₃ A Ca ₃ (Al,Fe) ₂ O ₆	Cubic Orthorhombic: O _I and O _{II} Monoclinic [7]
	Orthorhombic (Ca,Na ₂)Ca ₈ Al ₆ O ₁₈		Replacement of Ca ²⁺ by Mg ²⁺ [19], Na ⁺ [7], K ⁺ [19], Sr ²⁺ [20]. Replacement of Al ³⁺ by Fe ³⁺ [19], Si ⁴⁺ [19]
Ferrite (C₄AF)	Ca ₂ (Al,Fe) ₂ O ₅	Ca ₂ (Al,Fe) ₂ O ₅	Two orthorhombic phases depending on Al/Fe ratio [21] Replacement of Al ³⁺ by Fe ³⁺ (whole range)[21], insertion Mg ²⁺ [21], Mn ³⁺ [22] and Ti ⁴⁺ [23] on Al/Fe sublattice
Lime (CaO)	Monoxide	MeO	Cubic
Periclase (MgO)	(Ca ²⁺ ,Mg ²⁺ ,Fe ²⁺)O with Fe ³⁺ , Al ³⁺ , Ti ³⁺ , Ti ⁴⁺ in dilute solution	(Ca ²⁺ ,Mg ²⁺ ,Fe ²⁺ ,Sr ²⁺ , Al ³⁺ ,Fe ³⁺ ,Ti ³⁺ ,Ti ⁴⁺ ,□) O solution	(Ca ²⁺ ,Mg ²⁺ ,Fe ²⁺ , Sr ²⁺ , Al ³⁺ , Fe ³⁺ ,Ti ³⁺ , Ti ⁴⁺ ,□)O solution

For Aluminate (C₃A), this is represented in FTOxid with two polymorphs and three foreign elements in the crystal structure, Fe, Sr and Na, and GTOX portrait this phase with only one polymorph and Fe alone in solid solubility. The literature shows that solid solution of C₃A with K and Si are possible and four distinct polymorphs are possible depending on the doping amount of these elements and the other already characterized elements [7].

Finally, for Ferrite phases (C₄AF), no minor element insertion is represented on the commercial databases and only one polymorph is considered. However, the variation of Al and Fe is modelled from pure Fe to 80% Al as observed experimentally. Lime and Periclase are very well depicted by the existing databases due to the lower number of element interactions.

Clinker Simulations

Fig. 1: Two-step clinker prediction model.

2.1 Modelling approach

To perform any thermodynamic equilibrium calculation using Gibbs energy minimization, a temperature and (gas) pressure as well as the overall composition shall be set. The numerical input for the composition in the clinkering simulations is the chemical composition of the clinker as determined from X-ray fluorescence measurements. For the temperature, this is more complicated since reliable measurements in the rotary kiln are cumbersome to carry out. The overall gas pressure is set to 1bar.

To model the clinkering process, a two-step procedure is adopted for the simulations as seen in the flowsheet in Fig. 1. The first step corresponds to the sintering of the raw mix in the presence of a liquid at maximum clinkering temperature (T_{\max}) in the rotary kiln. The assumption is that the resulting phase assemblage from this step is close to thermodynamic equilibrium. The main difficulty here is to evaluate the maximum burning temperature in the sintering zone.

Note that in-situ measurements are not reliable due to dust often present in the kiln; hence, an indirect calculation method was chosen for the high temperature step. Specifically, the amount of liquid phase in the sintering zone should be between 20 and 30 % by mass – set based on process experience. For lower values, the clinker becomes dusty; while for higher values, it becomes sticky. Thus, ~25 % is a compromise and the maximum sintering temperature is then calculated by a target calculation fixing the amount of liquid at equilibrium.

Given the composition of the raw meal fed to the kiln, the equilibrium is calculated in the first step with a rough initial estimate of the maximum temperature inside the kiln (1420°C), then iterated to get the 25 % by mass of liquid. The result of this high temperature step are the amounts of alite, primary belite, lime and periclase with a total amount of 75 % by mass of the mixture along with the liquid phase. The

presence of belite or lime depend on the lime saturation of the raw meal. The presence of periclase depends on the MgO level. The amounts of the solid phases are saved and are not used in the cooling step.

The cooling step is simulated starting from the amount and composition of the liquid phase and assuming a Scheil-Gulliver type cooling behavior [24]. As already stated, this implies, that the already formed solid phases do no longer contribute to the equilibrium calculation and only precipitation from the liquid phase is accepted, assuming a homogeneous liquid throughout the sample. In principle, a double cooling step is needed, one for the oxidic liquid and one for the salt melt (mainly sulfates), as the two tend to unmix on cooling. However, in this contribution, the calculation was simplified and only the oxidic liquid is considered. The remaining sulfates are grouped together in one block.

2.2 Numerical simulations

To test the validity and the quality of the evaluated databases and benchmark results, data from [25] – a relatively recent publication – served as a reference. In this reference study, industrial clinker mineralogic compositions were determined for eight Portland type clinkers, seven grey clinkers (i.e., PC-(A-G)) and one white Portland clinker (i.e., WPC) using standard Laboratory X-ray Diffraction (XRD or LXRD) and Synchrotron X-ray Diffraction (SXRD). Four clinkers were selected for our simulations to cover the standard composition space of typical OPC clinkers (PC-A, B, E and F).

Table 2 summarizes the input clinker composition, which stems from XRF measurements and is renormalized to Loss on Ignition (LOI) = 0 for simulation purposes.

Table 2. Chemical composition of Portland Clinkers renormalized to LOI = 0.[25]

Oxide	PC-A	PC-B	PC-E	PC-F
SiO ₂	20.49	19.68	20.37	21.32
Al ₂ O ₃	5.26	4.26	4.75	5.05
Fe ₂ O ₃	3.58	3.79	2.37	4.24
CaO	65.22	61.05	65.02	65.65
MgO	1.62	6.68	3.34	0.52
SO ₃	1.20	1.60	1.77	1.42
K ₂ O	1.02	0.24	1.29	0.70
Na ₂ O	0.49	0.09	0.49	0.13
P ₂ O ₅	0.14	0.82	0.14	0.17
TiO ₂	0.27	0.53	0.23	0.28
Mn ₂ O ₃	0.06	0.20	0.08	0.16
SrO	0.61	0.80	0.11	0.26
ZrO ₂	0.03	0.25	0.04	0.10

2.3 Results and Discussions

The mineralogical compositions from the simulations using FactSage's FTOxid and GTOX databases as well as the classical Bogue equations as compared to the experimental LXRD and SXRD data are listed in Table 3 for the selected samples.

First, all calculations using FactSage's FTOxid database lead to wrong mineralogical compositions since they do not show any Alite prediction, the most important phase in Portland Clinker. This is distinctly odd since all simulations from the literature using this database show Alite as a stable phase – even being accompanied by minor elements [3]. Thus, the Gibbs energies of pure Ca_3SiO_5 in the presence of other elements is incomplete (see Table 1) and likely wrong.

The results from GTOX database agree better with data from [25]. Calculating the mass percentual difference of the most accurate of the techniques in [25], namely SXRD, GTOX predictions for Alite are 7.1% less for the PC-A, 21.2% less for PC-B, 6.3% less for PC-E and 6.7% more for PC-F. These are higher than the commonly accepted uncertainty of XRD Rietveld analysis results ($\pm 3\%$). One possible source for the difference is the quality of the XRF measurements and the acquired data accuracy. For Alite, a 0.3 % mass difference in CaO quantity in the initial data can lead to a 2- 3 % variation in the final result. Thus, high quality input data, information about the machine and experimental techniques uncertainties help obtain proper simulation results. However, the main source for the difference is the thermodynamic model used in the database. Alite is taken as stoichiometric without any minor elements. However, as stated above, Alite can dissolve considerable amounts of Mg, Al, Fe and alkalis which makes it thermodynamically more stable, i.e., a more negative Gibbs energy. As the calculated Alite values in sample A, B and E are lower than the measured ones, this goes in the right direction. The alite level in sample F is higher in the calculation which is not possible from a thermodynamic point of view and presents an outlier. The observed difference can thus not be explained from the missing insertion of minor elements in alite only.

As for Aluminate and Ferrites, calculations using GTOX yield greater inaccuracies when compared to Alite metrics. In cases such as PC-B and PC-F, no C_3A is present in the results. This is likely due to the crucial role of alkalis in the Aluminate phase stability and the insertion of Si into the crystal structure, both additions demonstrated to have specific changes in the polymorphism of C_3A . In addition, this absence can be attributable to the simplification that provides the Scheil-Gulliver model as this model assumes a homogeneous melt with respect to composition which would assume an infinitely fast diffusion of the elements in the melt. It is obvious that this is a theoretical and oversimplified case.

Concerning the maximum sintering temperature, the results of the simulation agree with the common knowledge. It is possible to simulate the liquid quantity by setting a higher or lower temperature in order to create a sensitivity analysis for the burning process. For instance, for a certain mix or input composition the plotted percentage of Alite versus the change of maximum temperature of the process would give a curve in which the slope is the sensitivity of that mix.

Table 3. Mineralogical compositions of Portland Clinkers calculated by XRD, SXRD [25], Bogue and FactSage simulations.

	T_{\max} (°C)	Alite	Belite	Alumi- nates	Ferrite	Lime	Port- landite	Periclase	Sulfates	Quartz	Calcite	Other
PC-A	XRD	76.0	3.0	6.0	12.1			0.5	2	0.3	0.3	
	SXRD	77.1	3.0	5.2	12.3		0.1	0.4	1.7	0.2		
	<i>FTOxid</i>	1370		59.1	10.5	5.9	18.6		0.9	2.5		2.6
	<i>GTOX</i>	1365	70.0	4.6	2.3	10.4	2.4		1.5	2.4		5.4
	<i>Bogue</i>		69.2	6.5	7.9	10.9						
PC-B	XRD	53.8	22.2	1.8	14.3			7.5	0.5			
	SXRD	55.9	21.0	2.2	13.7			6.4	0.5			
	<i>FTOxid</i>	1435		58.4	9.5	6.5	15.2		5.9	2.5		1.4
	<i>GTOX</i>	1430	34.7	31.3		7.8	8.7		6.7	1.7		8.8
	<i>Bogue</i>		64.9	7.5	4.9	11.5						
PC-E	XRD	71.3	6.4	7.0	5.9		1.2	3.3	2.3	0.6	2	
	SXRD	74.7	4.7	7.3	4.4		1.6	2.2	2.1	0.3		
	<i>FTOxid</i>	1350		58.6	10.4	2.5	19.6		2.7	3.6		2.8
	<i>GTOX</i>	1462	68.4	6.2	4.7	6.5	3		3.2	3.6		4.2
	<i>Bogue</i>		74.6	2.1	8.6	7.2						
PC-F	XRD	58.4	23.6	3.5	11.9		0.1		2.4			
	SXRD	60.8	22.2	3.4	10.7		0.8		1.9			
	<i>FTOxid</i>	1380		61.5	9.4	9.1	15.6		0.3	2.7		1.4
	<i>GTOX</i>	1445	67.5	10.3		11.9	1.4	0.4		1.6		6.9
	<i>Bogue</i>		65.2	11.9	6.2	12.9						

A steep curve in this case means that process control is more difficult for this specific input composition. Such a tool helps improve raw mix design – since the model can be used to suggest initial mixture that are more temperature stable, preparing or reacting to plant control system for specific operational kiln conditions. An example of this is shown in Fig. 1, showing that lowering the temperature on 20°C it is possible to get approximately 1 % by mass more of Alite.

Finally, the occurrence high values for free lime and periclase are likely due to the incomplete and inaccurate database for higher MgO contents and phase descriptions. As Mg is dissolved in all major phases, free Periclase should be lower. The origin of high free lime is due to the inaccurate modeling of the binary CaO-Al₂O₃ system in the high lime region.

In summary, FactSage's calculations with FTOxid show an immense and irreparable discrepancy with XRD and SXRD analysis with a poor performance as a predictor of the mineralogy in a Portland Clinker sample. Namely, it shows no Alite in the final mineralogy at all. As for GTX, it performs fairly well and shows a clear direction on how a base commercial dataset can be improved. Nonetheless further work shall be done to advance the current state of Portland Clinker mineralogy prediction with the incorporation of the minor elements in the mineralogical phases which are missing in the current versions of the two databases.

Fig. 2: Sensitivity evaluation example for Alite in PC-E in the range of 1400 to 1500°C using GTX database.

3 Conclusion

This study demonstrates that CALPHAD-based models can provide a versatile platform for predicting clinker mineralogy under AF-influenced conditions. However, they require considerable improvements in the existing Gibbs energy datasets to account for minor elements as active elements instead of mere additions.

The provided methodology identifies specific database deficiencies (e.g., MgO in C₃S and C₄AF, alkali content in C₃S and C₃A, etc.) that limit predictive accuracy and proposes a framework for iterative improvement through experimental-thermodynamic coupling. Based on the obtained results, a necessary improvement for the

Gibbs energy databases is to formulate the interaction between C_3S , C_2S , C_3A and C_4AF and the minor element not represented in the studied databases (e.g., Fe, Al, Mg, Na, K, S, P, Ti and Mn). This will likely provide a better foundation for FactSage's Gibbs energy minimizer and yield realistic outputs.

To conclude, the optimization of clinker composition via the studied models with their improved Gibbs energy datasets, can help cement industry reduce AF-induced variability, directly lowering energy consumption and emissions in clinker production. Future research should focus on expanding thermodynamic descriptions to include minor elements' interactions with defects and phase characterization as well as integrating real-time process data for adaptive kiln control systems. Ultimately, such advancements could redefine sustainable clinker production by aligning mineralogical quality with circular-economy fuel strategies.

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